

LINGUISTIC EFFECTS ON TELEVISION ADVERTISEMENT: A STYLISTIC APPROACH

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of the article is to search on advertisement style of the texts as well as stylistic devices which are used in mass media text. Moreover, some stylistic tropes are given in the article which are used in the advertisement style.

KEY WORDS: advertising, linguistic elements, copywriters, stylistics, stylistic tropes.

Text is one of the best ways for people to communicate. Texts can be written or spoken depending on their appearance. Writing is done for a number of different purposes and for different audiences. These different forms of writing are often known as text types. Factual texts inform, instruct or persuade by giving facts and information while literary texts entertain or elicit an emotional response by using language to create mental images. Over the decades, a specialized form of language has developed within the Uzbek as well as many countries' context of advertising. It is an English language, yet a language already subjected to purposive and medium variation. This has, in turn necessitated some substantial, structural and semantic variations. Regarding to Crystal and Davy (1969:11), 'any use of language displays certain linguistic features which allow it to be identified with one or more extralinguistic contexts'. Advertisement as a form of business communication has wide spectrum of outlets such as film, television, radio, fax, newspaper, magazine, telephone, face-to-face conversation, etc. Television as a channel of communication has become a veritable medium through which advertisers transmit the messages on their products to teeming viewers because of its peculiarity of being able to combine visual and pictorials for the purpose of communication. The purpose of the advertiser is very specific. They wish to capture the attention of the members of the mass audience and by means of a short message, often written or verbal, but sometimes visual, to persuade them to buy a product or behave in a particular way. In order to achieve this, the language of television advertisement is usually characterized by identifiable distinctive linguistic features, stylistically conditioned to pass persuasive

messages to viewers. These distinctive features distinguish the English Language used in advertising from other standard varieties, thus, worthy of academic attention. It can be mentioned without any doubt that the advertisement can affect people's mind with the help of its strong and persuasive meaning. Therefore, in this type of writing source people's mind can be altered. The stylistic features of the language of advertisement identified in the sampled advertisements are ellipsis, substitutions, coordination, contraction, repetition, simple sentence and declarative sentence; all used distinctively as style. Content may be subject to copyright. It is a style of immediate impact and quick persuasion. Stylistic advertising has its own features in morphology, syntax, and rhetorical devices. Looking at the advertising text stylistically, one can analyze that mass media text can be persuasive and informative. Especially, advertising text is persuasive which is intended to persuade people to use the service or to purchase the advertized thing. Advertising is very vital for all businessmen as well as customers as it gives full information about the product. However, advertising should be so strong to take people's attention so various types of stylistic devices are used in the advertising text. For instance, the followings can be mentioned:

1. Metaphor - transferring the properties of one object or phenomenon to another according to the principle of their similarity, hidden comparison: Sunny Travel Package ("INNA TOUR" travel agency); Starlight on your lips (lipstick Avon).

2. Epithet - a figurative description that gives an additional artistic quality: A winter's tale... this is about Andorra. A wonderful country, magical nature, wonderful ski mountains, great weather, comfortable hotels and gourmet cuisine. Your winter vacation is sure to be wonderful! ("Neva" travel agency); Refreshing aroma (Nescafe coffee).

3. Hyperbole - artistic exaggeration: Sea of happiness. Turkey (Turkey advertisement); The whole planet is at your disposal ("Planet Earth" travel agency); Stimorol. Try (gum "Stimorol"),

4. Litots - artistic understatement: a part of the world called Holland; Malta is a small pearl of the Mediterranean! The World in Your Pocket (Reader's Digest magazine); Feel like a goddess (stra Venus).

5. Personification - transferring the properties and qualities of a person to an inanimate object: Azimuth. Your convenient companion ("Azimut" chain of hotels for business trips, Russia); German quality. Impeccable style. Male character (home appliance advertisement Bork)", Touch the work: beautiful,

intellectual, sexy (telephone ads Nokia)", a car with a spacious interior can be called "hospitable" (car Mitsubishi Outlander XL).

6. Comparison - subject or semantic similarity of events; A comparison to illustrate two things and phenomena with each other: the Maldives, like a huge swarm of jellyfish; Beautiful as day, mysterious as night (Avon perfume "Earth Woman").

7. Metonymy - replacing one word with another depending on its neighborhood: China does not forget its roots and traditions, restores ancient monuments ("Southern Cross" travel agency); There are more than 50 museums in Stockholm ("Otdykh.ru" tourist agency).

8. Precedent texts - the use of texts that are available at the level of background memory of native speakers: How beautiful this world is, look! ("Upton" travel agency); Think for yourself, decide for yourself (Advertising for a bus tour around Europe - "7 days"); All roads lead to Rome!(Italy travel ad).

9. Rhetorical question - unanswered question: Is this really Switzerland? ("White Stripe" internet magazine); And what is the New Year in Uzbekistan? (^ travel agency "Central Asia Travel"). As can be seen from the above materials, the range of stylistic tools used by advertisers is extremely wide, and their purpose is to influence the mind, intellect and imagination of potential buyers. Connecting stylistics and advertising with each other gives several arguments to the scientists.

Style is a way of choosing a particular language tool from among several possible ones, and the principle of connecting different tools with each other. There are three aspects of style: axiological, functional and normative. According to the axiological style, the style is high (the language of odes, eulogies, appeals, tragedies, etc.), low (the language of humor and comedies, in which colloquial and colloquial units are used) and medium (neutral general literary words) it can. Due to the diversity of messages, it is very difficult to describe the axiological aspect of advertising style, but the following can be noted: basically, advertising uses medium style, using elements of high and low style, depending on its goals and objectives. (advertising message).

However, the language of the advertising message directly depends on the target audience and the definition of the general purpose. Any technical product is difficult to describe in everyday language. If you refer to experts, you can also use scientific and professional rules and terms that are relevant to the target group.

The normative aspect describes the degree of conformity to the stereotype of the presentation of the material. On the one hand, advertising must be unique in order to attract consumer attention, on the other hand, a typical representative of the target audience is not interested in the linguistic ingenuity of the developers of the advertising text, but in its own character. personal benefit from a product or service. Therefore, when creating an advertising text, first of all, you should always keep in mind the scale and purposefulness of the presentation.

To sum up all given facts, theories, ideas, it can be said that there are several principles of style, the text of the advertisement should correspond to: Abbreviation - Disadvantages are general, abstract and abstract thinking. The main task here is to quickly get to the essence of the message. It is recommended to save sentences, get rid of redundant words, especially adjectives, but not to sacrifice phrases that are necessary to maintain style and rhythm. Thus, the advertising message must meet the minimal requirement: minimum words - maximum information. Accuracy and precision - It is important that the ad "sells" exactly what is being advertised. specific item, and not all products of that type, so it is necessary to focus clearly on the USP (unique selling proposition). Details build credibility in an ad. If you can write "man", you should not write "male", if you can write "accountant Semyon Semenovich, 37 years old", you should not write "man". However, boring and unnecessary details that make perception difficult should be avoided.

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